

Database	Search Date	Search String	Search Fields	Filters	Results Identified*
CINAHL Ultimate	2025-11-03	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	All fields	No filters applied	168
	2025-11-03	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	All fields	Full text (selected searches)	1
	2025-11-03	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	All fields	Full text (selected searches)	3
	2025-11-03	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	All fields	Full text (selected searches)	30
	2026-06-02	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	All fields	No filters applied	320
Cochrane Library	2025-11-14	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	Title, abstract, keyword	No filters applied	12
	2025-11-14	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Title, abstract, keyword	No filters applied	0
	2025-11-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Title, abstract, keyword	No filters applied	1
	2025-11-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	Title, abstract, keyword	No filters applied	6
	2026-06-02	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse")	Title, abstract, keyword	No filters applied	29

OR "psychological abuse" OR
 "emotional abuse" OR "financial
 abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND
 (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)

MEDLINE	2025-11-03	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	All fields	Text words	39
	2025-11-03	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	All fields	Text words	1
	2025-11-03	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	All fields	Text words	2
	2025-11-03	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	All fields	Text words	35
	2026-06-02	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	All fields	Text words	82
ProQuest Ebook Central	2026-01-14	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	Keyword, full text	No filters applied	1
	2026-01-14	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Keyword, full text	No filters applied	0
	2026-01-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Keyword, full text	No filters applied	0
	2026-01-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	Keyword, full text	No filters applied	1
	2026-06-06	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR	Keyword, full text	No filters applied	0

		"emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)			
PubMed	2026-01-14	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	Title/abstract	No filters applied	98
	2026-01-14	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Title/abstract	No filters applied	3
	2026-01-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Title/abstract	No filters applied	5
	2026-01-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	Title/abstract	No filters applied	88
	2026-06-06	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Title/abstract	No filters applied	278
SAGE	2026-01-15	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	Abstract	No filters applied	7
	2026-01-15	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Abstract	No filters applied	0
	2026-01-15	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Abstract	No filters applied	0
	2026-01-15	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	Abstract	No filters applied	6
	2026-06-06	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial	Abstract	No filters applied	24

		abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)			
Scopus	2026-06-09	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	Article title, abstract, keywords	No filters applied	360
	2026-06-09	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Article title, abstract, keywords	No filters applied	7
	2026-06-09	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Article title, abstract, keywords	No filters applied	8
	2026-06-09	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	Article title, abstract, keywords	No filters applied	257
	2026-06-10	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Article title, abstract, keywords	No filters applied	674
SpringerLink	2026-01-16	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail* [Keywords] (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail* [Title]	No filters applied	0
	2026-01-16	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	elder AND (abus OR mistreat) AND (pre-frail OR prefrail) [Keywords]	No filters applied	27
	2026-01-16	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Keywords	No filters applied	110
	2026-01-16	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail* [Keywords] (violen* OR abus*) AND frail* [Title]	No filters applied	1

	2026-06-07	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") [Keywords] (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*) [Title]	No filters applied	411
Taylor and Francis Online	2026-01-15	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	Abstract	No filters applied	25
	2026-01-14	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Abstract	No filters applied	0
	2026-01-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Abstract	No filters applied	0
	2026-01-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	Abstract	No filters applied	19
	2026-06-07	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Abstract	No filters applied	57
Web of Science	2026-01-26	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND frail*	Topic	No filters applied	136
	2026-01-26	elder* AND (abus* OR mistreat*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Topic	No filters applied	4
	2026-01-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND (pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Topic	No filters applied	6
	2026-01-14	older* AND (violen* OR abus*) AND frail*	Topic	No filters applied	141

2026-06-08	(elder* OR older*) AND (abus* OR mistreat* OR maltreat* OR violen* OR neglect* OR "physical abuse" OR "psychological abuse" OR "emotional abuse" OR "financial abuse" OR "sexual abuse") AND (frail* OR pre-frail* OR prefrail*)	Topic	No filters applied	300
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*Search results represent records retrieved before deduplication and screening.